

◆ Research Paper

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Community Attributes and Impact of Cult Related Activities across Selected Communities in the Niger Delta

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Abstract: This study examined the disastrous impact of cult related activities on selected communities in Niger Delta region from 1999-2017. Using a cross-sectional design, the study explored the impact of cult related activities on communities, and the characteristics of vulnerable communities. The population of the study was made up of households of selected communities impacted by cult violence. Sample size was derived using the Taro Yamane equation and copies of the questionnaire were administered for data collection. The result showed that for cult impact on the communities, assassination, displacement and looting were ranked highest, while rape and shut down of health and worship centres were ranked least among the impacts identified. Among the assets impacted, residences, health facilities and farmlands were ranked highest while communication and security facilities were ranked least. The result further revealed that social activities such as hanging out, age grade meetings, social belonging and political power struggle were prevalent in communities mostly impacted by cult attacks while socio-economic characteristics of such places includes high illiteracy, petty trading, crude oil production, farming activities, illegal crude oil bunkering, poverty and high unemployment. In addition, issue such as land dispute, chieftaincy tussle, cultural festivities and town union events were prevalent in these communities. It is

recommended that initiation of social investment programs as intervention measure to empower youths and keep them engaged should be considered for these areas

Keywords: Cult-related Activities, Cult Violence Impact, Community Attributes, Niger Delta

Introduction

According to Olokesusi (2005), disasters both natural and man-made have caused major losses of human lives and livelihoods, destruction of economic and social infrastructures in the past four decades. Conflicts, wars, terrorism, armed related violence and civil unrest are some of the man-made disasters leading to significant humanitarian crisis and disasters across the world (United Nations Development Program, UNDP, 2014). At the same time, armed conflicts remained persistent for many communities and countries globally (Walch, 2013). In 2010, out of the thirty active armed conflicts recorded by the United Nations Development Program, four caused a minimum of 1000 deaths – Iraq, Afghanistan, Pakistan and Somalia (Walch, 2013). The World Development Report 2011 estimated that more than 1.5 billion people live in countries stricken by armed conflict including acts of terrorism and cultism (as in the case of Niger Delta). Most of the ongoing conflicts are internal with high civilian casualties (UNDP, 2014). Nigeria, especially the Niger Delta has not been spared in the devastating effects of the armed conflicts with cultism and terrorism wreaking great havoc. The Boko Haram insurgency in the North East, Herdsmen attacks in the Middle Belt and cult related activities in the Niger Delta region, have all created humanitarian crisis and their escalation have had grave consequences for the livelihood of the citizenry. It is because of these devastations that this study aimed at examining the impact the cult activities on the people of River and Imo State. This study highlighted impacts on communities, impacted assets as well as the characteristics of these vulnerable communities. This is intended to provide an understanding of the dimensions of the impacts on and inherent characteristics of places with such violent activities in the region.

Views expressed by Birabil and Okanezie (2017), showed that cult violence in Niger Delta has assumed terrorism dimensions that pose threat to the country with potential for turning into war. This is because, cult attacks have resulted in mass killing of civilians,

destruction of properties, disruption of social, cultural and economic activities, subjecting residents to huge psychological and mental trauma. Just as the contemporary terrorism, the major characteristic of cult attacks is its unexpectedness. Chung (2013), observed that the time and manner of attacks are unpredictable and catches targeted communities especially the innocent civilians by surprise. In the past, targets were often rival cult members not the general public, but the purposes and targets of contemporary cult attack are unclear, making it more difficult to prevent. Ogbondah (2014) identified the dimensions of the cult related activities in Niger Delta to include, kidnapping, armed robbery, sea piracy, pipeline vandalism, burning of houses, beheading of people, prostitution, rape of women, drug abuse and threat to life among others. This was corroborated by Partnership Initiative in the Niger Delta (PIND, 2015).

Findings by PIND (2015), revealed that inter cult attacks evolved in communities in Niger Delta region in mid 1990s but were elevated in 2015 when it assumed terroristic dimensions. Nyiayaana (2011), inferred that the emergence of cult groups in the region was facilitated by the formation of two militant groups, the Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force (NDPVF) and the Niger Delta Vigilantes (NDV). Cult groups such as the Deewell and Deebam emerged from the two militant groups. PIND (2015) in its report observed that since 2015, fatalities and devastations cause by the cult related activities have been huge and alarming compared to the mid-2000. The findings show that inter-cult killings were insignificant (not of serious concern) in the area in the early 2000. However, by late 2014, cult attacks assumed terroristic dimensions at the peak of political campaigns for 2015 general elections and has since then, remained a terror to the civilian populace in Niger Delta. For instance, as reported by PIND (2015) since 2014, fatalities resulting from cult related armed conflicts increased alarmingly particularly in Rivers State, with a single conflict causing as far as 17 deaths (Chinwo, 2018; Nwankwo, 2017; Olowolagba, 2018 and Onoyume, 2017).

In response to this menace, the Governments of Rivers and Imo States offered an amnesty/disarmament program to the armed cultists to surrender their weapons and repent (Chinwo, 2017). The is meant to pardon those cultists once they gave up their arms and embrace peace and the rehabilitation program instituted. At the end of the program, a total

of 23,160 and 3,073 cult members from different cult groups surrendered their arms and embraced the program in Rivers and Imo State respectively in 2016 (Chinwo, 2017). Unexpectedly, the violence persisted after the amnesty declaration, increasing the risk of cult violence and overwhelming the capacity of the respective States Government to contain the situation. At this time, the Government of Rivers State solicited the support of the Federal Government for a large scale military intervention, as well as announced a bounty of N840 million for provision of any information that could lead to arrest of the cult gangs terrorising the State (Inyang, 2018; Ukpong, 2018).

With the definition of disaster as an occurrence disrupting the moral conditions of existence and causing a level of suffering that exceeds the capacity for management of such by the affected community (WHO, 2002). The call for external support showed that the menace has exceeded the capacity of the State government, using only immediate resources available to them.

For the purpose of this research, a cult group is a group or gang especially youths whose beliefs, actions and behaviours are considered as extreme or strange by many people and engage in criminal activities which intimidates and make the residents feel unsafe. Cult related activities include criminal activities perpetrated by cult members either in groups or individually, which impact negatively on the security of the community and its resources. Such activities include inter/intra cult violence, invasion of communities by armed cult gangs, kidnapping/abduction, inter-communal violence, sea piracy, illegal oil bunkering, rape, political thuggery/killings and armed robbery. According to UNICEF (2012), cult activities include inter/intra cult violence to defend and control territory, drug trafficking, oil bunkering, reputation for being brutal, among others.

Like gangs, cults operate in order to provide economic gain for their members. However, they also tend to be more organised around defending certain territory - often in defense of a neighborhood or ethnic group within an urban area (UNICEF, 2012). They have rules and rituals and are more strongly organised than are gangs. Those present in the university system evolved from confraternities and may be loosely affiliated to outside cults or across different universities.

Nyiyayanna (2011) affirmed that the cult violence in Rivers State has spread to villages with serious implications on social order and stability and called for urgent steps to be taken to address it. The author further remarked that although most cult clashes/violence occur mainly due to battle for supremacy and territorial control by different cult groups, the struggle for social identity and the expression of economic discontent by disaffected village youths are key elements fuelling cult violence in the State. Corroborating this assertion, Chinwo (2018) posited that the killing of the seventeen (17) persons in Omoku, who were returning from the 2018 New year crossover church service was the fallout of the supremacy fight among rival cult groups in the area. Also, Onoyume (2017) opined that at Mgboshimili community, about fifteen (15) persons were shot dead and many houses burnt down in a single attack carried out by members of the Icelander cult group over battle for supremacy and territorial control.

PIND (2015) explained that this cult violence elevated in 2015 with more fatalities and devastations than the previous years since mid-1990s when cult-related violence peaked in the State. The report identified four (4) cult groups as the major cult groups operating in communities in Rivers State, causing the escalation of cult violence and the worsening insecurity. They are;

- i. Deebam Cult Group
- ii. Deewell Cult Group
- iii. The Icelanders Cult Group and
- iv. The Greenlanders Cult Group

Methods and Materials.

This study was conducted in Imo and Rivers States which are the two Niger Delta States that granted amnesty to cultists in 2016. The Niger Delta is located along the Atlantic coast which forms the southern boundary of Nigeria. The region has an estimated area of about 70,000km² and is one of the world's largest deltas. It is in the central part of southern Nigeria (Fig. 1). The 2017 projected population of the Niger Delta is 44,229,729, comprising the total

population of the nine (9) States that make up the political Niger Delta (Abia, Akwa Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Imo, Ondo and Rivers). The region represents about 12% of Nigeria's total surface area (NDDC, 2006).

Figure 1 Niger Delta State with study area States (Shaded)

Source: Authors' representation

The design of the study was a cross-sectional survey carried out across to States – Rivers and Imo States. The States were exclusively chosen because of their administration of

Amnesty Program to cultists in 2016. The population of the study comprised the entire population of the selected 36 communities (Fig. 2 and 3) which were chosen because of the high prevalence of cult attacks and the administration of Amnesty in them by the government. Taro Yamene's formula was applied on the 1,009,162 being the entire population of the 36 selected communities to give a total sample size of 400 used for this study. Copies of questionnaire (both structured and unstructured) were used for data collection. The structured questionnaire was administered to community respondents while the unstructured questionnaire was administered to key informant/stakeholders within each of the communities sampled. Out of the 400 copies of questionnaire administered to community respondents, a total of 379 copies were retrieved. To measure the cult impact on communities and assets, 5- point Likert scale was adopted. The rating is as follows, Very High Extent (VEH=5), High Extent (HE=4), Moderate Extent (ME=3), Low Extent (LE=2) and Very Low Extent (VLE=1). Weighted mean was used to rank the magnitude of the responses among the categories (items).

Figure 2 Selected Communities in Rivers State

Source: Authors' representation

Figure 3 Selected Communities in Imo State
 Source: Authors' representation

Results and Discussion

Impact of Cult Activities

From the result in Table 1, killings was ranked the highest in term of cult impacts as perceived by the respondents across the communities. This is followed by displacement of people, looting of shops, destruction of livelihood, abandonment of farms and disorganisation

of age grade meetings which ranked 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th and 6th respectively. According to Nnodim and Ochogbu (2018), cult impacts on communities in Niger Delta have been huge. This is largely attributed to the inter-cult wars with rival cult groups fighting for control of an area and for the award of surveillance jobs of the oil facilities by multi-national companies. Abductions, schools disrupted/shutdown, houses burnt, women raped, shutdown of health and worship centres ranked 7th, 8th 9th, 10th, 11th, and 12th respectively on cult impacts on the communities.

Table1 Respondents’ Responses on Cult Impacts on Communities

S/N	Items	VHE 5	HE 4	ME 3	LE 2	VLE 1	Total	Weighted Mean	Ranks
1	Houses are burnt	158	63	86	24	48	379	3.68	9
2	People are displaced	221	57	46	22	33	379	4.08	2
3	Farms are abandoned	166	97	43	21	52	379	3.80	5
4	People are killed	219	69	46	20	25	379	4.15	1
5	Schools are disrupted/shutdown	142	96	67	37	37	379	3.71	8
6	Women are raped	139	73	83	29	55	379	3.56	10
7	People are abducted	167	76	65	21	50	379	3.76	7
8	Health Centres Shutdown	124	68	106	36	43	379	3.50	11
9	Livelihood are destroyed	174	86	57	27	35	379	3.89	4
10	Age grade meetings disorganised	162	69	88	22	38	379	3.78	6
11	Worship Centres are Shutdown	117	84	81	51	46	379	3.46	12
12	Shops are looted	215	33	59	21	51	379	3.90	3

Source: Researcher’s Field Work and Data Analysis, 2019

Majority of those engaged in Key Persons Interview (KPI) stated that the impacts of cult related activities have been so severe that women became afraid of going to farms to avoid being raped. They revealed that it was to the extent that many residents had to relocate to other areas where they feel safer. According to one Francis (not the real name), a respondent from Obakpu community, Ohaji/Egbema LGA of Imo State:

Between 2015 and 2016, we experienced cult crisis/violence to the extent there was no buying and selling. Nothing was moving in the community in general. Many people changed positions, changed environments, and became visitors in their new places of residents because the cult groups subjected them to stringent rules on how to leave and operate in the own community. That time schools, markets, shops even churches were shutdown totally. Everything was brought to a standstill with hunger all over the place. The two major cult groups in the area engaged themselves in serious fight and struggle for dominance and

control of the area. People hardly sleep, we were hearing gunshots every day, killings were rampant, people were assaulted in different ways, women raped in the farms, many unusual things happened due to cult clashes. There was panic everywhere, innocent people were also killed. If your son or relation is a member of the opposing gang they are looking for, when they come and they don't see him, they will shoot or kill any of the parents around or any relation they see as a way of sending message to the other cult gang and the runaway cultists.

Table 2: Respondents' Responses on Assets Impacted

S/N	Items	VHE 5	HE 4	ME 3	LE 2	VLE 1	Total	Weighted Mean	Ranks
1	Health facilities	72	79	97	57	74	379	3.05	2
2	Communication facilities	41	21	72	66	179	379	2.15	10
3	Bank facilities	89	55	61	83	91	379	2.92	4
4	Residential buildings	107	80	97	72	23	379	3.46	1
5	Farmlands	69	81	61	95	73	379	2.94	3
6	Government structures	51	41	112	61	114	379	2.61	7
7	Commercial buildings	90	31	62	89	107	379	2.76	6
8	Security facilities	40	45	105	63	126	379	2.50	9
9	Market facilities	55	55	105	97	67	379	2.83	5
10	Others	51	42	97	59	130	379	2.54	8

Source: Researcher's Field Work and Data Analysis, 2019

Assets Impacted by Cult Activities

From Table 2, residential buildings, health facilities, farmlands, bank facilities and market facilities ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th among the assets impacted by cult related activities. Other assets such as commercial buildings, government structures and other facilities ranked 6th, 7th and 8th respectively while security and communication facilities were least impacted having ranked 9th and 10th respectively. The result shows that cult related activities have had impact on community assets and has consequently affected assets, livelihood and amenities for the communities.

Table 3: Distribution of Responses on Characteristics of the Study Area

Characteristics	High		Low		Nil	
	count	%	Count	%	count	%
Social						
Age grade meetings	251	66.23	86	22.69	42	11.08
Social camping	92	24.27	223	58.84	64	16.89
Social belonging	194	51.19	93	24.54	92	24.27
Social Night clubbing	104	27.44	84	22.16	191	50.40
Hanging out	189	49.87	97	25.59	93	24.54
Fitness training	98	25.86	192	50.66	89	23.48
Political power struggle	251	66.23	68	17.94	60	15.83
Different languages	180	47.49	80	21.11	119	31.40
Inter marriages	270	71.24	68	17.94	41	10.82
Economic						
Illiteracy	289	76.25	59	15.57	31	8.18
Petty trading	317	83.64	52	13.72	10	2.64
Crude oil Production	246	64.91	98	25.86	35	9.23
Crop Farming	256	67.55	88	23.22	35	9.23
Fish farming	222	58.58	134	35.36	23	6.07
Hunting	204	53.83	118	31.13	57	15.04
Livestock farming	211	55.67	114	30.08	54	14.25
Illegal Crude oil bunkering	206	54.35	82	21.64	91	24.01
Poverty	331	87.34	45	11.87	3	0.79
Unemployment	339	89.45	36	9.50	4	1.06
Cultural						
Land dispute	197	51.98	130	34.30	52	13.72
Chieftaincy dispute	201	53.03	118	31.13	60	15.83
Communal dispute	124	32.72	194	51.19	61	16.09
Cultural festivities	258	68.07	92	24.27	29	7.65
Idolatry	116	30.61	214	56.46	49	12.93
Vigilante	122	32.19	216	56.99	41	10.82
Town Unions	221	58.31	118	31.13	40	10.55

Source: Researcher’s Field and Data Analysis, 2019

Characteristics of Communities with Persistent Cult Violence

From Table 3, the result shows that among the social characteristics, age grade meeting (66.23%), social belonging (51.19%), hanging out (49.87%), political power struggle (66.23%) and intermarriages (71.24%) were high in the communities with cult related activities. Also, for economic characteristics, illiteracy (76.25%, petty trading (83,64%),

crude oil production (64.91%), crop farming (67.55%), fish farming (58.58%), hunting (53.83%), livestock farming (55.67%), illegal crude oil bunkering (54.35%), poverty (87.34%) and unemployment (89.45%) were high in the communities. On cultural characteristics, land dispute (51.98%), chieftaincy dispute (53.03%), cultural festivities (68.07%) and town unions (58.31%) were high in the communities with cult related activities.

Discussions

The results revealed that the impact of cult activities was high and disastrous in the study area. Respondents indicated that the disastrous impacts have been huge with killings, displacement, looting, destruction of livelihoods, abandonment of farms, disorganisation of age grade meetings, and abduction. This research further showed that the cult activities had impacted on community assets with impact on residential buildings, health facilities, farmlands, bank facilities, market facilities, and commercial buildings. The findings of this research corroborate findings by Nnodim and Ochogba (2018) which identified some of the impacts of cult activities to include kidnapping, looting and raping of women. A study conducted by International Crisis Group (2018) in El Salvador, Central America showed that gang wars has resulted in massive killing of people as well as forcing many residents to search for safety even outside their residential areas (displacement). According to World Bank (2017), the impact of violent conflicts are escalating across the globe, affecting peoples' means of livelihoods negatively as well as causing displacement of residents. As found by this research, the cult impact affected community assets such as health facilities, banking facilities, residential buildings, commercial facilities, market facilities, security facilities, government structures and farmlands among others. This impact of cult related activities on community assets is assuming disastrous dimensions. This is because as found by Nwaogu and Ezekwe (2018) asserted that a disaster event impacts community assets such as health facilities, residential buildings, public infrastructure, and farmlands. As cited in United Nation's Report of March, 2019 on conflict in Syria, the violence has caused destruction of assets such as health facilities, school facilities, banking facilities and government structures.

This study found that there are specific characteristics common to vulnerable communities irrespective of their locations. Consequently, it is assessed that those peculiar

characteristics could have increased the vulnerability of the area to cult related activities. This finding is in line with findings by Nnodim and Ochogba (2018) that socio-economic characteristic of rural dwellers in Orashi region of Rivers State with persistent cult violence includes, age grade meetings, camping/hanging out, drinking with friends, fish farming, and hunting. Nyiayaana (2011) identified some of the features of communities with cult related activities in Ogoniland of Rivers State to include prevalence of land dispute, chieftaincy tussle, poverty and high unemployment rate.

Conclusions and Recommendation

Based on the findings of this research, it is concluded that the impact of cult related activities was significant on the communities. This has left the communities with enormous challenges to contend with using their own resources and could have a negative spiral of making these places more susceptible to cult activities and its attendant problems.

Addressing the prevalence of cult related activities in communities in Niger Delta region is important in ensuring peace, stability and safety of the people as well as improving their wellbeing. Therefore, based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were deemed relevant:

- Government should work with the local communities in designing an intervention programs for youths
- Employment opportunities should be provided for youths to keep them engaged.
- Local government areas in collaboration with security agencies should build comprehensive database for cultists in their areas.
- Programs that reward ex-cultists should be discouraged while programs to reward only youths who do not belong to any cult group should be initiated at community levels.

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